

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 –GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D4.2: Testing of the produced materials for the removal of metal ions and for the absorption of targeted molecules used as a model of environmental pollutants

REPORTING PERIOD	
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RM4 Responsible	Daniele Dondi

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List of Deliverables

D. No	Name	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)
D 4.1	Report on plant/bacteria consortia efficiency for the removal of metal ions from wastewaters	REPORT	PU	M24		
D 4.2	Report on the adsorption performances of porous solids derived from biomasses valorization and non-recyclable plastic wastes	REPORT	PU	M24		09/04/2025

CONTENTS

Report on the adsorption performances of porous solids derived from biomasses valorization and non-recyclable plastic wastes.

The topics mentioned in this report are the following:

- The porous materials prepared in Task 2.2.4 (Arlorio, Laurenti) and Task 3.1 (Broggini, Zanetti) will be tested and compared in the adsorption and/or degradation of targeted compounds
- Removal of heavy metals and organic substances from simulated and real polluted water matrices, using different strategies.

A) INTRODUCTION

UPO: UPO, in collaboration with the Task partners, has initiated the testing of silica and aluminosilicate-based solid supports derived from agro-food chain waste (rice husk), prepared in task 2.2, for the removal of organic pollutants and heavy metals from water media, as well as for the recovery of metal ions of technological interest.

UNIPV: The activities are divided into three main categories: dairy water treatment (Magni), bioremediation with algae (Pinnola) and photocatalysis/ porous polymers (Dondi). A greater integration in between output wastewater coming from other activities in RM4 was considered too.

UNITO: On the basis of the flagship project, a group of the most promising porous materials prepared in task 2.2.4 and task 3.1 were properly selected to be tested as adsorption supports for the removal of organic and inorganic compounds from water matrices.

B) ROLE OF PARTNERS

UPO (Chiara Bisio, Stefano Marchesi): evaluation of the adsorption and exchange capacities of biogenically derived porous silica and clay materials, prepared in task 2.2, in the removal of various contaminants (organic dyes and metal ions) from simulated and real polluted water media. Besides, part of the experiments and analyses were also conducted in collaboration with the Task partners (Unito).

UNIPV (Paolo Magni): Improvement of the prototype for the treatment of dairy wastewater for the preparation of bioethanol and introduction of the regulatory system to render the prototype ready to market. (Alberta Pinnola, Chiara Milanese) Use of secondary byproducts coming from other wastewater treatment (including also Magni's output). (Daniele Dondi) Assessment of photo catalysts and irradiation setup for the degradation of emerging organic pollutants (antibiotics, dyes). Development of porous (sponge) polymers for microplastics (in collaboration with Oviedo University, Spain), heavy metal and rare-earth elements removal from wastewater (the latter two in collaboration with UNITO).

UNITO (Luca Rivoira and Maria Concetta Bruzzoniti): application of selected materials produced in task 2.2.4 and task 3.1 to be tested as adsorbent for the removal of organic and inorganic pollutants in water matrices.

C) EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

UPO: The first stage of the study involved the use of mesoporous silicas obtained from the transformation of rice husk (UPO, Task 2.2) for their ability to adsorb rhodamine B (RhB) dye from simulated polluted waters. This was done using batch experiments performed in simple conditions. This organic pollutant, which is frequently present in wastewater from the textile industry, was selected due its distinctive UV-Vis absorption characteristics, allowing for the observation of its removal from water by UV-Vis spectroscopy. The experiments were conducted by placing the biogenic silica-based adsorbents (0.1 g) in contact with 20 mL of a 0.02 mM Rhodamine B solution, under stirring at room temperature and ambient pressure. At different contact times (between 0 and 24 hours), samples of the supernatant liquid was taken and, after centrifugation, the absorbance was

measured by means of UV-Vis spectroscopy.^[1] From the absorption spectra of the dye remaining in solution collected over time, dye adsorption curves were obtained as a function of contact time. For the purposes of statistical analysis, three replicates were conducted for each experiment, and the results were compared to those of similar reference solids. The obtained results demonstrated that the target contaminant was almost completely removed from water after 20 minutes of contact with the adsorbents. Subsequent tests were also performed at low RhB concentrations (RhB solutions of ca. 0.0025 mM) and yielded similar results. CHN analysis^[2] confirmed the presence of the adsorbed organic dye on the tested silica-based supports.

Subsequently, UPO evaluated the possible use of a cation-exchange layered material derived from rice husks (i.e. saponite clay) for the removal of heavy metal ions (especially Mn and Fe) from samples of real contaminated drinking water. The latter was provided by a local water supplier company. The exchange performance of the saponite materials was evaluated in comparison to an analogous reference clay. Batch experiments were conducted by introducing 0.02 grams of biogenic saponite clay into 1 milliliter of a Mn- and Fe-polluted drinking water. This water had been filtered and the pH level had been adjusted to approximately 3 before analyses. Tests with contact times ranging from 1 to 24 hours were analyzed using analytical techniques, namely ICP-MS, from which metal capture curves over time were derived for each sample.^[3] The results demonstrated a high Mn ion capture capacity (>90% of the initial concentration) by the biogenically-derived saponite clay, with a reduction of the metal concentration below the Italian legal limits for drinking water (50 ppb) within a few hours (<3 h). Further evaluation of the removal of Fe, As and other heavy metals, including Cr ions, from polluted drinking water supplied by the local water company of Alessandria, is currently underway. In future studies, these batch experiments will also be conducted under flow conditions.

Finally, in collaboration with Unito (Luca Rivoira and Maria Concetta Bruzzoniti), a series of tests are currently underway to evaluate the adsorption and removal capacities of a range of organic pollutants (including PCBs, PAHs, herbicides, endocrine inhibitors, and heavy metals) in both simulated and real polluted waters. These tests utilize the aforementioned silica- and aluminosilicate-based solids (and related reference materials), and the complete results will be presented in future reports.

UNITO: Following a fruitful discussion among all the Partners involved in the task, the following supports were selected to be tested as adsorbents:

- Clays and silica-based supports (both from traditional synthesis and obtained from rice husk) synthesized by University of Piemonte Orientale (Prof. Chiara Bisio and Dr. Stefano Marchesi), for a total of 9 different supports
- Hydrogels synthesized by University of Pavia (Prof. Daniele Dondi), for a total of 9 different supports

Adsorption tests were performed towards different classes of pollutants typically affecting natural water compartments (and, therefore, included in the main European and local legislations). In detail, removal tests were performed on: i) 10 heavy metals (namely Al, As, Cd, Cr, Cu, Fe, Hg, Mn, Ni, Pb), as representative of the inorganic pollutants class; ii) 8 Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs), 13 Polychlorobiphenyls (PCBs, including some dioxin-like congeners), as representative of the planar and aromatic pollutants class; iii) glyphosate, as

representatives of the herbicides class; iv) 4-nylophenol and bisphenol A, as representative of the endocrine disruptors class.

For each class of compounds, a proper analytical technique was optimized, in particular heavy metals should be analyzed through ICP-OES, PAHs, PCBs and endocrine disruptors by SPME-GC-MS and glyphosate by IC-HPLC

Adsorption tests were planned to be performed in batch conditions for both classes of materials, but the conditions were different depending on the type of the material.

In particular, the removal tests using hydrogel supports were directly performed in the laboratories of the University of Pavia and the conditions are, hence, elsewhere described. The post-extraction solution were sent to our laboratories to be analyzed.

Conversely, the adsorption test of material belonging to the University of Piemonte Orientale were internally performed and the conditions were chosen following the previous know-how developed by our research group. In particular, a proper amount of each sorbent (0.1g) was put in contact with 17ml of a water solution spiked with target pollutants (each class separately). The suspensions were stirred for 24 hours, filtered using a nylon 0.45 μ m membrane filter and then analyzed using the above-mentioned analytical techniques. For each material two independent replicates were performed.

Adsorption yields were calculated following this equation:

$$\text{Adsorption yield \%} = 1 - (C_a/C_s) \times 100,$$

where, C_a is the concentration of the target compound detected in the solution put in contact with the tested sorbent and C_s is the concentration spiked in the batch before the adsorption test.

Adsorption tests are still in progress and the results will be presented within the following deliverable.

UNIPV: Increase of the TRL of the bioreactor for the production of bioethanol and assessing the regulatory system. In general, a greater interchange of products and treatment was tested, in order to create a multistep treatment procedure (bioremediation, UV irradiation, Physisorption).

The preliminary bibliographic screening on microplastics topic, in cooperation with Oviedo University (Spain), lead to the publication of one review paper ^[4].

Bioplastic devices made by photo- or thermal polymerization starting from modified waste cooking oils were studied for the adsorption and physisorption of microplastics and dyes [paper submitted].

The enhancement of properties with respect to the shape and defined porosity was assessed by means of stereolithographic 3D printing.

The biopolymer devices were also tested for the adsorption of heavy metals (see previous section).

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